

Research Article

China's foreign aid and its impact on poverty, unemployment, infrastructure, economic development, and bilateral trade in Nigeria: Using a regression model

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Abstract: For the past few decades, China has provided constant development assistance to Africa of which Nigeria is not an exception. This assistance has been one of the most contentious issues in the continent. Notwithstanding, whether foreign aids are sufficient or insufficient, foreign aid has the potential in accelerating economic development, alleviating poverty, reducing unemployment, and increasing industrialization and infrastructural development. Foreign Aid and economic development, on the other hand, are inextricably linked. Foreign aid has an enormous impact on the recipient's economy and prosperity. However, proper utilization and appropriation of foreign assistance received matters in this regard, on how it will inure positive economic benefits is a course of concern. The research considers first-hand information on the kind of Foreign Aid sourcing from China and its significant impact on alleviating poverty, reducing unemployment, increasing industrialization and infrastructural development in Nigeria. Because proper utilization of Aid received and its management is a means to successful economic development and the deepening of bilateral ties between countries. Foreign aid received help in saving the lives of citizens, rebuilding the livelihood of people, providing medical care, developing agriculture for food security and export, encouraging the development of industry and technology, and proper exploration of natural resources for export, especially solids minerals. Besides, the country still needs further aid from other developed nations to support its economic development activities because issues of poverty, unemployment, and lack of social and economic infrastructures persist in the country. We conducted a thorough investigation to determine the impact of each variable on economic development and bilateral trade relation. For statistical analysis, we employed the multiple linear regression model and ANOVA test to establish the significant impact of the explanatory variables on economic development and bilateral trade relations. For instance, the findings suggest that Foreign Aid received impact positively on poverty alleviation, reducing unemployment, increasing industrialization and infrastructural development in Nigeria, as evident in our regression analysis (see *Table 7*). The findings made a significant contribution to existing knowledge in the areas of foreign Aid received, economic development, as well as bilateral trade relations between China-Nigeria. This research is in support of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal one. The results, therefore, provide a

roadmap for assessing and strengthening foreign aid policy and its benefit for economic development across the globe.

Keywords: Chinese Foreign Aid, management, Economic Development, Bilateral trade relations, Nigeria.

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Introduction

China and Nigeria are similar in terms of geographical and demographic importance on their respective continents. China has the second-largest economy in the world and one of the fastest-growing foreign aid programmes. Nigeria, as Africa's most populated black nation, is a country that cannot be overlooked in Africa due to its vast people and economic potential. Since Nigeria's independence in 1960, bilateral ties between China and Nigeria have improved dramatically. China has provided more foreign aid to Nigeria than any other western donor or international organization (Mthembu-Salter 2009). Aid assistance received from countries including China is making a substantial change in terms of poverty alleviation, disaster, and misery on the part of the receiver, such as Nigeria.

Aid is most commonly given in the form of official development assistance (ODA), which aims to reduce poverty while also promoting public welfare and economic development. China's aid to Nigeria has some issues that prevent it from being used properly and from being implemented following the agreement between the donor and the recipient Nigeria. Corruption in Nigeria impedes the proper use of these aids in credit or loans, and some items made for specific humanitarian aid material are diverted for personal use (Alege and Okodua 2014). The government's unwillingness to follow up on proper implementation by the agencies or ministries to which these aids were directed in Nigeria.

Insecurity and ethnoreligious sentiments in Nigeria have an impact on the economy and the intended victims due to political instability in Nigeria, many regimes, particularly military regimes, were unwilling to benefit from the bilateral relationship between China and Nigeria (Umo-Udo and Orifa) because democracy and diplomatic integration was not much grounded at that time. Though some countries were receiving and benefiting from different sources of foreign Aid, there was non-existence of proper legal frameworks and laid down policies between countries, such as Nigeria, and other countries during the military regime before gaining independence. This triggered issues of corruption, mismanagement and misappropriation of foreign aid received during such regimes of governance, and its multiplier effects on trade and investment. But the ultimate question borders around the fact that countries including Nigeria keep receiving Foreign Aid in all manner of forms, however, the region keeps experiencing issues of unemployment, and a lack of social and economic infrastructures that support economic development. Hence, investigation to strengthen public policy on economic development.

1.1 The objective of the Study

The purpose of this research is to investigate the economic development impact of foreign Aid received from other countries using China as a reference point and how it deepens bilateral trade relationships among countries. And how this impacts unemployment in the country. The following specific objectives were used to achieve the goals;

- ✓ To find out the impact of Chinese foreign Aid on economic development and bilateral trade.
- ✓ To find out the impact of Chinese Foreign Aid on unemployment reduction.
- ✓ To find out the extent to which Chinese Foreign Aid influence infrastructural/ industrial development.
- ✓ To find out whether Chinese Foreign Aid helps in poverty alleviation.

1.1.1 Research Hypotheses

To realize the objective of the research, the following hypotheses served as a guide to the research and its findings (see Table 7).

H1: Chinese Foreign Aid influences economic development and bilateral trade at (0.000) <0.05) significant P-Value.

H2: Chinese Foreign Aid reduces unemployment at (0.000) <0.05) significant P-Value.

H3: Chinese Foreign Aid impact positively on infrastructural/industrial development at (0.000) <0.05) significant P-Value.

H4: Chinese Foreign Aid reduces poverty at (0.000) <0.05) significant P-Value.

1.2 Significance of Study

Existing literature on Foreign Aid from countries like China, the UK, Germany, USA etc have largely focused on Africa in a broad sense and primarily from traditional donors, who have sought to explain the veil behind the Sustainable National Development and increasing trend in aid to Africa (Chukwu-Okoronkwo 2015), whereas this study will focus on Aid received from China to Nigeria and its management impact on economic development. The significance of this study is to identify some of the obstacles preventing the proper usage of China's aid to Nigeria in particular, as well as how this aid should be deployed to benefit Nigerian residents and economic growth. This study focused on Chinese aid management and its impacts on economic development and bilateral trade relation. The research empirically emphasized how this Chinese aid money is managed and its replica effects on economic development and bilateral trade relation. This research on Chinese aid to Nigeria, and economic growth and developmental impacts on the China-Nigeria relationship on the mutual principle of dependency theory of international relation and diplomacy. The study aims at helping the Nigerian government and policymakers understand how Chinese aid is managed to combat corruption, eradicate poverty, and create a proper legal framework and good climate for economic expansion. Again, the study will help Nigerian parliaments, the Ministry of External Affairs, the Ministry of Finance, Agriculture, sold minerals, policymakers, and students/scholars understand the effectiveness of Chinese aid on China-Nigeria trade relations as a tool for improving bilateral relations. Quite importantly, it will provide students and researchers with useful information in the fields of international ties and international political economy, as well as a stepping stone for further study and research on China's aid and its economic multiplier effect on trade and investment relationships with recipient states in Africa and around the world.

2 Literature Review

The main theoretical contribution of this work demonstrates the resourcefulness of all theories in supporting the identification of variables that are either directly or indirectly related to Foreign Aid and economic development. In terms of theoretical support, the dependency theory, which is associated with Marxist theories, contends that developed countries in their quest for power infiltrate developing nations through political advisors, missionaries, experts, and multinational corporations (MNCs) to integrate them into the capitalist system to appropriate natural resources and foster developing nations' dependence on developed nations. The link between China and Nigeria and its effects on the

growth of the Nigerian economy are best explained by this idea. Dependency theory holds that resources move from a "core" of wealthy governments to a "periphery" of poor and underdeveloped states, enriching the latter at the expense of the former.

The study of Chinese foreign aid and its growing relationship with Nigeria is an essential component of the research because it underpins the very fabric of China's aid to Nigeria. Against this backdrop, various authors have contributed their perspectives and analyses on the growing Chinese aid and the African states' relationship (Mohan and Lampert 2013). This study takes a look at a few of these scholars and their debates. Following the research objectives, this chapter presents a literature review and a theoretical framework. It discusses how aid can be used to rebuild livelihoods in Medicare, food, and other necessities because Aid given to countries is meant to improve the lives of people which will consequently lead to major improvements in economic development.

2.1 Concept of Aid

Foreign Aid and its management as a concept has been dominated by western developed countries, either through bilateral and multilateral agreements administered by the International Monetary Fund (IMF), World Bank, and United Nations (UN) (Kuziemko and Werker 2006, Grabel 2007, Steinwand and Stone 2008, Morrison 2012). The OECD development assistance committee (DAC), which is used by the West to facilitate aid to developing countries, has been changing its approach over the years; however, they have begun to experience new rising aid donor power with competition from emerging economies. China has extended loans to African countries for infrastructure development and trade flexibility, backed by decades of economic growth and a desire to increase international activities. Without the conditions for good governance and transparency that have always been requested and guided by western donor agencies such as the IMF and World Bank aid and loans (Steinwand and Stone 2008, Morrison 2012).

2.1.1 Types of Chinese Aid

Aid is received in the following forms: Namely, Money and materials are transferred directly. Export credit is quick, flexible, and unconditional loans for infrastructure development, Grants, interest-free loans, and loans with a lower interest rate Human resources, as well as technological cooperation, are essential. Assistance in the form of humanitarian aid and in-kind donations Aid to education and aid to the economy.

About 20% of the overall financial aid received by the committee of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development came from China. Between 2001 and 2011, development aid was provided. Unlike foreign aid from Western countries, which is generally in the form of direct money and material transfers, Chinese aid is primarily in the form of rapid, flexible, and mostly unconditional export credits and infrastructure investment loans. Africa-Nigeria is a priority region for China in terms of getting foreign financial aid China's formal development assistance to Africa has increased dramatically since the founding of the Forum on China–Africa Cooperation in 2000. Chinese international aid can be classed into three forms, according to a white paper produced by the State Council of China in 2011 on the country's foreign help: grants, interest-free loans, and concessional loans (China Africa Research Initiative 2017). Donations are largely utilized to assist recipient countries in the construction of hospitals, schools, and low-cost housing, as well as well-digging and water-supply projects, and other small and medium-sized social welfare projects. Grants are also employed in development cooperation, human resources, technical collaboration, and urgent humanitarian and in-kind aid initiatives (China's State Council Information Office, 2011). Interest-free loans are typically used to aid loan recipients in the development of public infrastructure and the implementation of programmes to improve their living standards. The average loan length is 20 years, with ten years of repayment, five years of use, and five years of grace.

Currently, interest-free loans are given mostly to developing countries in strong financial positions (China's State Council Information Office, 2011). Concessional loans are typically used to help loan recipients complete productive projects that create social and economic opportunities, such as medium- and large-scale infrastructure projects, or to provide mechanical and electrical products, complete plants, technical services, and other equipment. China's Export-Import Bank issues concessional loans on the market, and the difference between the loan interest rate and the People's Bank of China's benchmark interest rate is covered by the government as financial subsidies. Annual interest rates on China's concessional loans currently range from 2% to 3%, with payback lengths ranging from 15 to 20 years (including 5 to 20 years) (China's Information Office of the State Council 2011). Chinese aid is generally in the form of rapid, flexible, and unconditional export credits and infrastructure loans with low or no interest rates (Lin and Wang 2014, Wang, Yu et al. 2021). However, it is distributed throughout several areas, including emergency and economic development. It is largely distributed to a variety of sectors, including health, communication, education, infrastructure, energy, agriculture, trade and tourism, banking and financial services, and so forth (Guillon and Mathonnat 2019). Looking at some of the benefits of aid, it's clear that the primary purpose is to save lives. Foreign aid is there to save lives, especially in times of calamity, starvation, and disasters, such as natural disasters, where more than half of the world's population is living in deplorable conditions. Their food is insufficient, they are afflicted with sickness, and their economic situation is rudimentary and stagnant. Poverty is a barrier and a threat to them as much as more fortunate communities. For the first time in human history, humanity has the knowledge and skills to help these people (Andrews 2009). Below is a diagram illustrating the forms of foreign aid assistance received from China and other donor countries.

Figure 1 Kind of Foreign assistance.

Source: (Guillon and Mathonnat 2019). Official Development Assistance to African countries (2019)

2.1.2 Aids Granted to Nigeria

The Aids that are received in Nigeria includes Rebuilding livelihood-humanitarian aid, Medical aid- providing medicine, Agricultural aid, Technological transfer aid, Educational aid, Natural Resources aid, Developmental aid, Grants, Interest-free loan, Forgiveness of old loan, Aid in infrastructure, and superstructure like road, rail and ports construction and Guaranteed loan and others. The Aid received by Nigerians is meant to save the lives of the citizen, rebuild the livelihood of people, provide medical care, development of agriculture for food security and export, encourage the development of industry and technology, and properly exploration of natural resources for export, especially solids minerals.

Development aid helps people rebuild their lives by providing jobs and housing as soon as a tragedy strikes, allowing victims to get back on their feet. Medical missions are also accessible to deliver free medical and healthcare products and services in underserved communities. Foreign agricultural aid assists farmers and boosts food production, resulting in a better quality of life and more food. Industrial development projects sponsored by foreign aid provide more jobs, enhance infrastructure, and contribute to the local community's overall development. Other less developed countries are unable to maximize their abundant natural resources, but this is attainable with outside support (Ebiede 2018). The author, on the other hand, divides China's contribution to Africa into three categories, observing that China is neither a "new" nor an "emerging" aid donor. Since the Maoist era, it has provided aid to Africa and other sections of developed countries. Before that time, China's aid enters its second phase, with little growth in the 1970s and its final and current stage emerged in the 1990s when China's aid to Africa and other developed countries expanded beyond 11 political motivations. To more strategic ones that place a greater emphasis on achieving mutual economic benefits (Ebiede 2018). The effectiveness of aid in promoting economic growth has long been a key topic for policy discussion, and various perspectives—both favourable and unfavourable—have evolved from successive waves of study (Carter 2014). The relationship between aid and growth is the topic of the first two papers in this special issue. It is not unexpected that econometric methodology has been a major point of worry given the myriad factors that affect growth itself and the possibility of endogeneity. The various findings regarding the relationship between aid and growth found in the literature (Dalgaard, Hansen et al. , Clemens, Radelet et al. 2011, Juselius, Møller et al. 2014) are largely a result of the choices made regarding the econometric models used, the use of data (and whether data points are excluded), as well as the estimation methods used. According to (Arndt, Jones et al. 2010), a model of supply-side factors at the donor-recipient level is used to instrument help. The findings of the study by Arndt et al. in this special issue demonstrate that aid has not just simulated growth but has also encouraged structural transformation, enhanced social indicators, and long-term reduced poverty (but has no significant effect on inequality). There is evidence that investments in physical and human capital are a key way that help has a favourable impact on growth (through funding improved provision of infrastructure as well as healthcare and education). Not just the amount of aid and its direction are significant; fluctuations are also crucial. A commitment to increase predictability in aid is made in the Paris Declaration from 2005 (OECD 2005, OECD 2011). What influence does assistance volatility have on how well it promotes development? A growing number of people have expressed concern about this (Bulir, Gelb et al. 2007, Celasun and Walliser 2008). Aid is more variable overall as a source of funding for development than other government revenue sources (Bulíř and Hamann 2008). The total amount of help is the result of numerous donor decisions, sometimes coordinated, often not (Knack and Rahman 2007). The 2003 Rome Declaration on Harmonization, the Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness, the 2008 Accra Agenda for Action, and the 2011 Busan Partnership for Effective Development Cooperation are just a few of the measures made to address the situation throughout time (OECD 2005, OECD 2011). According to a growing body of research (Younger 1992, Adam and Bevan 2006), while effective aid can boost an economy's supply side (for instance, through improved infrastructure), it also has the potential to harm growth through its demand-side effect. Aid raises demand, and because the supply of non-tradables is inelastic, the relative price of non-tradables (including exportables) might increase relative to that of tradables, hurting total growth when tradables are the growth driver.

2.2 Aids Management and Economic Development

The effect and effectiveness of aid can be influenced by how it is managed. Aid management is essential for ensuring that aid fulfils its intended purpose in economic development, including successfully moving from its current state to a higher one. Redefining partnerships and promoting ownership, improving coordination, enhancing capacity building and change management capacity, lowering transaction costs by improving aid delivery mechanisms, donor policies, and practices, improving budget management systems, and maintaining the exit strategy are all proposals for improving aid management. An exit strategy is essential from two perspectives. First, donor-side variables may cause aid to be curtailed. Second, because the goal of aid is to help the recipient become self-sufficient, the recipient country should endeavour to graduate from aid dependency at some point. The exit strategy includes building the ability to accomplish development goals, debt relief, and direct foreign investment to reverse capital flight, domestic resource mobilization, and export development. This aspect of the research has so far reviewed pertinent literature that sheds light on China's aid and Nigeria-China relations. The majority of the literature studied the general role and reasons for China's help to Africa, attempting to fill a gap in this research on how China's aid should be properly handled to bring about the development required to nurture China-Nigeria relations.

2.3 Conceptual framework

Every conceptual idea requires specific knowledge management in a specialized area to function (Clement, Huaicheo et al. 2021, Mintah, Gabir et al. 2022). Even though certain foreign aids obtained from donors come with conditions attached. The idea of official development assistance (ODA) suggests that the assistance that is received has the potential to lessen the severity of issues such as poverty and inequality, maintain or increase levels of income, cut down on levels of unemployment, and stimulate economic growth and development across nations. However, in the process of accomplishing this goal, the appropriate administration of aid and assistance received from donor countries and the appropriate application of such administration for overall economic development are important factors to consider (Wangwe 1997). Hence, the article focused on establishing a strong relationship from theoretical and empirical findings based on the construct variables as framework-specific (see Figure 2). The fundamental idea is to gain an understanding of the effects that Chinese foreign aid, in all of its various forms, has on other construct variables such as the reduction of unemployment and poverty, the expansion of industrial and infrastructure development, and the acceleration of economic growth, following Official Development Assistance and the first Sustainable Development Goal of the United Nations.

Figure 2 Hypothetical framework

Source: Author’s Design, (2021)

3 Methodological Approach

3.1 Profile of the study area, Technical Route and Research Framework

The study was conducted in Nigeria to establish the relationship between Chinese aid management and its impact on Nigeria's economic development and bilateral trade. Nigeria is located on the western coast of Africa. Below is a sketch map of the study location.

Figure 3 Map of Nigeria

The route of inquiry or examination reflected specific goals derived from the research query by identifying the sources from which the data was planned, obtained, and analyzed. This helped in addressing appropriate questions and how to evaluate the related thesis question formulated.

Shows the technical framework.

Figure 4 Technical Route and Research Framework

3.2 Research Design and Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods used in terms of research design, study population, survey and sampling methodology, instrumentation, data collection, interpretation, and statistical analysis. This segment usually responds to the issue of "How" the study was carried out. Since it is the foundation on which the research process and findings are based. In other words, the section forms the architectural design of the whole research process, from start to finish.

There are various data collection methods aimed at evaluating China's aid management and its impact on economic development and trade relations. The survey design approach was followed in the study. Respondents were purposefully sampled to elicit their views on China's foreign aid and economic development in Nigeria, and trade relations. Questionnaires in the form of closed-ended questions were used (Likert scale). The Ministry of education, Transport, Health, Agriculture, Telecommunication, National Disaster management, and the Central Bank make up our sample frame. Both primary and secondary data were used, although data analysis was done with primary data. SPSS version 25 was used for data processing and analysis, with the linear multiple regression model, ANOVA, and Durbin Watson test used to determine reality.

3.3 Research Design

The design is an exploratory study that took a survey design approach. This allowed the researchers to use questions to elicit responses from people with extensive knowledge of the subject. The study design was appropriate for achieving the survey objectives and answering the inquiry questions (Cooper, Schindler et al. 2006). This is a qualitative research method used to gain a better understanding of issues related to China's Foreign Aid and its management/utilization as well as its construct effect on accelerating economic development, alleviating poverty, reducing unemployment, and increasing industrialization and infrastructural development. Data on Foreign Aid management/utilization and its effects on economic development and bilateral relations were gathered purposely from institutional managers, supervisors, and accountants. The information gathered was subjected to thematic analysis.

A qualitative (descriptive) research design was adopted in this study. The design was chosen based on the nature of the research topic or issue, the researcher's personal experiences, and the study's intended audience (Borrego, Douglas et al. 2009).

Qualitative research, on the other hand, is an inquiry process of understanding" in which the researcher creates a "complex holistic picture, analyses language, reports comprehensive viewpoints of informants, and conducts the study in a natural context (Hanson, Creswell et al. 2005). Every study's architecture is formed by research design, which specifies how the study will be developed (Kumar 2018). According to (Hanson, Creswell et al. 2005) research designs are strategies and procedures for research that cover everything from general assumptions to specific data collection and analysis approaches.

3.4 Study Population

Aziato and Korsah (2014) referred to the population as the sum of all objects, subjects, or people who meet a set of requirements. In this study, the population comprises all people such as the Ministry of education, Transport, Health, Agriculture, Telecommunication, National Disaster management, and the Central Bank make up our sample list with different socio-demographic characteristics, who are benefiting, and responsible for managing the ODA in Nigeria.

3.5 Sources of Data and Data collection instrument

Every social science study necessitates a decision about how to collect data, analyze the data, and interpret the results to achieve the research objectives. Therefore, whatever the source or sources of data may be on the topic being studied, there is the need to consider the type of data, the forms of data, the time dimension and the methods of data collected (Blaikie 2003, Blaikie 2018). This explanation may seem to be common knowledge to experts, however, they are relevant knowledge in academic research and professional writings because it offers useful theoretical knowledge to the reader.

Primary and secondary data were used to compile this report. While qualitative data and first-hand knowledge were collected directly from important informants, Secondary data was gathered from books, newsletters, annual reports of organizations, and the internet using data tools like structured questionnaires and semi-structured interview guide to delve deeper into the issue of Chinese foreign aid, management/utilization and its impact on Nigeria's economic development and bilateral trade.

3.6 Sample frame

Data was purposely collected from a list of respondents from the Ministry of education, Transport, Health, Agriculture, Telecommunication, National Disaster management, and the Central Bank were among the potential respondents in this study. Since the list of respondents constitutes individuals with in-depth knowledge and may understand the purpose of this work. Hence, their inputs are required to generalize the subject under consideration and its implication on the construct variables.

3.7 Sample size Determination Procedure

According to (Adcock 1997, Walter, Eliasziw et al. 1998, Dell, Holleran et al. 2002), a sample is a subset of the entire population that is examined to generalize the research findings. As a result, sampling can be defined as selecting any subset of a population or universe as representative of that population or universe. This method was used to estimate a sample of 295 respondents from Nigeria's various. Yaro Yamane sample size determination formulae were adopted. This sample of respondents may seem small however it imparted the study. According to (De Vaus and de Vaus 2013) the ultimate purpose of sampling is to reflect the complete population. In research, sampling conserves resources, labour, and time while allowing for a higher level of overall accuracy than full enumeration (Moser and Kalton 2017). (Yemane 1967) as cited in (Israel 1992), mathematical formulae will be the best preferred for determining a representative sample of 295 as a valid sample for the study. The formulae provide a standardized margin of error and confidence levels per a given population as a guide to justify the desired sample required for a valid examination of a social phenomenon.

Determining sample size for this study was arrived at by employing the mathematical formulae as follows;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(\alpha)^2} \dots\dots\dots \text{eq (1)}$$

Where:

n= Desired sample size

α= margin of error (0.05) at 95% level of confidence

1= constant

N= Total population

Using the formulae

n=?

α= (0.05)²

1= constant

N= 800

$$n \geq \frac{1125}{1 + 1125(0.05)^2} = 295$$

3.7.1 Sampling techniques

The study used purposive sampling under the non-probability sampling approach to acquire responses on the subject matter. In purposive sampling, individuals, groups, and locations that are "information rich" are examined for selection (Patton 2014). Because the study's goal was to determine the influence of Chinese aid management on Nigeria's economic development and bilateral trade, hence experts and institutions with in-depth expertise on the subject matter were chosen such as the Ministry of education, Transport, Health, Agriculture, Telecommunication, National Disaster management, and the Central Bank.

3.8 Model Specification, and Variable definition

The impact of foreign aid management on Nigeria's economic development and bilateral trade was investigated in this article. In the Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) model, the analysis followed a predictable pattern. The research was modelled on five (5) variables, as specified and described below;

The general form of our empirical multiple regression model is as follows:

$$CFA = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 PA + \beta_2 RU + \beta_3 II + \beta_4 EDBT + \varepsilon$$

Where;

CFA=Chinese Foreign Aid

PA=Poverty Alleviation

α =Trend/Constant

β =Coefficients

RU=Reduced Unemployment

II=Industrial/Infrastructural Development

EDBT=Economic Development and Bilateral trade

ε =Error of term

4 Data Presentation and Discussion of the result

Descriptive Statistics of Respondents

The descriptive statistics of our respondents are shown in Table 1. The data for this study came from seven Nigerian organizations: the Ministry of education, Transport, Health, Agriculture, Telecommunication, National Disaster management, and the Central Bank. Inferring from the data, the majority of our respondents, 62 per cent, were males, while 38 per cent were females. The research considers first-hand information on Foreign Aid from the receiving country's

(Nigerian) and management perspective rather than legal administrators for managing Chinese Aid itself. It demonstrates that the men are actively involved in the management of Chinese aid in Nigeria. Again, 13% of our respondents were between the ages of 20 and 30, 24% were between the ages of 31 and 40, 25% were between the ages of 41 and 50, 35% were between the ages of 51 and 60, and 4% were over 60. Even though the active class was considered for the research, we discovered that a quarter of our respondents who are supposed to be retired are still working. A PhD is held by nine of our respondents, with a master's degree accounting for 48% and a bachelor's degree accounting for 43%. This suggests that educational attainment plays a role in firm organizational management. The findings from the demographic characteristics of our respondents show that a higher percentage of our respondents are married, accounting for 61%, 17% are single, and 14% and 8% are divorced and widowed, respectively. Social demographic characteristics of respondents matters in research because they highlight and give a vivid description of the respondents whom information was gathered from. Again, according to our survey, 55% of our respondents are in managerial positions, while 38 per cent and 7% work in accounting and supervision, respectively. This indicates that information was obtained from respondents who have firsthand knowledge of the subject matter to validate the credibility of our research findings.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics for the Sample. N= 295

Variables		Frequency	Per cent
Firms/Organizations (Valid)	Central Bank of Nigeria	65	21
	Ministry of education	22	7
	Health	42	14
	Telecommunication	33	11
	Agriculture	44	15
	National Disaster management	50	17
	Transport	45	15
Gender (Valid)	Female	112	38
	Male	183	62
Age (Valid)	20-30	37	13
	31-40	70	24
	41-50	73	25
	51-60	103	35
	60+	12	4
Marital Status (Valid)	Single	50	17

	Married	179	61
	Divorced	41	14
	Widowed	25	8
Educational Level (Valid)	PhD	26	9
	Masters	142	48
	Bachelors	127	43
Business role (Valid)	Accountant	112	38
	Supervisory	21	7
	Managerial	162	55
Total		295	100

Field survey, (2021)

Table 2 below reflects the statistical description of the variables; the results show that the variables are not significantly different from one another. The same samples were obtained. In terms of values, the minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviations are virtually identical. This means that the variable is not dispersed further from the mean. The standard deviation values for the variables are generally low.

Table 2 Statistical Description of all Variables applied in the Data Analysis

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
CFA	295	1	5	4.113	0.749
PA	295	1	5	4.117	0.752
RU	295	1	5	4.081	0.761
II	295	1	5	4.142	0.713
EDBT	295	1	5	4.131	0.707
Valid N (listwise)	295				

Field Survey, 2021

Table 3 Test for Validity and Reliability

variables	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
CFA	0.811	4
PA	0.811	4

RU	0.807	4
II	0.810	4
EDBT	0.789	4

Field Survey, 2021

In research, a reliability test indicates that the data used must regenerate or repeat the same results when a similar approach is used. In this case, the data can reproduce similar results if a similar methodological approach is applied (Golafshani 2003). Testing for dependability is important since it pertains to the consistency of a measuring instrument's parts. Cronbach's Alpha is a reliability coefficient that shows how well elements in a data collection are positively associated. Cronbach's alpha tests were used to determine the reliability of the multiple-question Likert scale questionnaires. The Cronbach Alpha helps in measuring the inter-correlation among internal consistency and reliability of test items. But mostly the acceptable measurement is set to fall between 0.7 to 0.9 (Landau and Everitt 2003). The Cronbach Alpha for all scale of measurement variables is justified within the measurement of constructs of 0.7 to 0.9. This simply implies a high correlation between the items and the questions set for the survey. The value is an indication that our questionnaire used for the study has satisfied the reliability test.

Here, validity determines whether a study accurately measures what it was designed to measure as well as the accuracy of the investigation's findings. According to (Golafshani 2003), construct validity is a term used in research to describe the validity of a study. The construct is the original thought, query, or hypothesis that guides which data should be collected. The goal is to ensure that the instrument is adequate and representative of all of the variables being measured. It was modified to make it clear to eliminate the uncertainty of items before the final distribution.

Table 4 Pearson Correlation Coefficient: Correlation matrix

Variables	Model	CFA	PA	RU	II	EDBT
CFA	Pearson Correlation	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
	N	295				
PA	Pearson Correlation	.998**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000				
	N	295	295			
RU	Pearson Correlation	.752**	.748**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000			
	N	295	295	295		
II	Pearson Correlation	.653**	.653**	.497**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000		
	N	295	295	295	295	
EDBT	Pearson Correlation	.819**	.817**	.741**	.559**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
	N	295	295	295	295	295

Note **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From Table 4, PA is strongly correlated with CFA (.998**) at a 1% significant level. This is an indication that China's foreign Aid has a significant impact on Poverty alleviation or reducing poverty. This idea is supported by (Mahembe and Odhiambo 2019) indicating that foreign aid has a positive impact on poverty, as reported by the majority of studies in both the non-momentary and monetary measures of poverty groups. CFA correlated with EDBT (.819**) at a 1% significant level. This indicates that there exists a relationship between CFA and EDBT. The results in the matrix show clearly that foreign aid correlates with economic development and bilateral trade relationships.

4.1 Regression Analysis

4.1.1 Durbin Watson statistic test

The sample adequacy was determined using the Durbin-Watson statistic test for variable model analysis. The value of 1.891 was obtained in this example, showing a positive autocorrelation. It was found to be higher than expected.

Table 5 Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change in Statistics	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig.	F	Durbin-Watson
.841 ^a	0.708	0.704	0.385	0.708	0.708	175.725	4	290	0.000	175.725	1.891

Predictors: (Constant), CFA, PA, RU, II

b. Dependent Variable: EDBT

In table 5, the R-value of 0.841 indicates a high level of prediction. The independent variable explains 70.8% of the variability in our dependent variable. Factors other than the predictors account for 29 (100% -71%) of the variation.

Table 6 ANOVA Test

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	104.134	4	26.034	175.725	.000b
Residual	42.963	290	0.148		
Total	147.097	294			

^a Dependent Variable: EDBT

^b Predictors: (Constant), CFA, PA, RU, II

To compare the variables in table 6, the analysis of variance was performed using two or more factors. Using the F-ratio in the ANOVA, the total regression model was checked for a good fit to the data (see Table 6). According to the table, the difference series of residual point values is 290, while the sum of squares series of residual point values is 147.097. As evidenced by F (4, 290) = 175.725, p (.000).05, the independent variable is statistically significant in predicting the dependent variables (the regression model fits the data well).

Table 7 Standardized Coefficients values (Multiple Regression)

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	0.638	0.147		4.325	0					
CFA	0.271	0.045	0.291*	6.058	0	0.741	0.335	0.018	0.523	1.912
PA	0.305	0.088	0.283*	6.056	0	0.853	0.499	0.040	0.540	1.851
RU	0.271	0.045	0.291*	6.058	0	0.741	0.335	0.192	0.814	1.228
II	0.262	0.055	0.292*	6.067	0	0.843	0.404	0.029	0.573	1.744

a. Dependent Variable: EDBT

The statistical significance of the dependent variable on the independent variable is shown in Table 7. Per the test results, CFA is statistically significant at $p(0.000) < 0.05$. This suggests that CFA has a positive impact on EDBT. PA, RU, and II, on the other hand, are statistically significant at $p(0.000) < 0.05$, $p(0.000) < 0.05$, and $p(0.000) < 0.05$, respectively. This result indicates that foreign aid received from countries including China in any form impact poverty alleviation (PA), reducing unemployment (RU), increased industrialization (II) and eventually on economic development and bilateral trade relations (EDBT). This research is in line with Tanveer, Latif et al. (2019) which indicates that foreign aid has positively contributed to employment generation which invariably reduces unemployment and poverty. The collinearity with variance inflation values, on the other hand, are all less than 10, indicating that the data set lacks a multicollinearity diagnostic.

Table 8 Residuals Statistics

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	2.58	4.63	3.79	0.364	295
Std. Predicted Value	-3.324	2.306	0.000	1.000	295
Standard Error of Predicted Value	0.105	0.367	0.224	0.048	295
Adjusted Predicted Value	2.50	4.61	3.79	0.372	295
Residual	-2.939	2.316	0.000	0.993	295
Std. Residual	-2.890	2.277*	0.000	0.976	295
Stud. Residual	-2.971	2.365	0.001	1.005	295
Deleted Residual	-3.119	2.499	0.001	1.052	295
Stud. Deleted Residual	-3.021	2.388	0.000	1.009	295

Mahal. Distance	1.695	32.005	11.953	5.469	295
Cook's Distance	0.000	0.061*	0.005	0.007	295
Centred Leverage Value	0.007	0.126	0.047	0.022	295

a. Dependent Variable: EDBT

The data set has a normal distribution, as shown by the standard residual value of the predicted variables on the dependent variable, which is -2.890 and can be found in the table that was just presented. Because when plotted, the usual residual value never goes beyond a range of minus two to plus two. However, the cook's distance of all of the predictor variables, in this case, is 0.061, which suggests that a value has an influential impact on the variable that is being studied.

5 Discussion of results

We established five (5) objectives before the study to navigate the relationship between Chinese foreign aid, poverty alleviation, unemployment reduction, increased industrialization and economic development as well as bilateral trade relation in Nigeria. To better understand the significance and mutual relationship that exists between variables, six areas in Nigerian that includes the Ministry of education, Transport, Health, Agriculture, Telecommunication, National Disaster management, and the Central Bank were purposefully chosen to determine the influence of Chinese foreign aid, on poverty alleviation, unemployment reduction, industrialization and economic development and bilateral relations. More importantly on how important these factors impact economic success. This will improve and leverage better means and innovative ways of channelling or distributing resources to positively influence economic development and other economic variables of interest. Foreign Aid received benefits and sustain the economy in all spheres (social, economic and political) (Chenery 1967, Hopkins 2000). As a result, having a basic understanding of foreign aid/assistance received from countries, its application and implication on other economic constructs (poverty alleviation, employment/unemployment and industrialization) and its ripple effect on economic development. The statistical significance of the construct variables will ensure economic success and deepen the donor-recipient relationship. The findings of this study make an important contribution to existing knowledge on foreign aid and the economic development of nations in all aspects. The results from the regression analysis (coefficients) of the variables disclose that foreign Aid (Chinese) received positively influences economic development and deepens bilateral relations. The results indicate that Chinese Aid received by the Nigerians and its proper utilization/management will invariably lead to poverty alleviation, reduced unemployment, and increase industrialization/infrastructures (Alvi and Senbeta 2012, Mahembe and Odhiambo 2019). This has a long-term effect on economic development and bilateral trade relations. This research is a means to strengthen policy support for foreign aid because it has a positive implication on economic development and bilateral trade.

6 Conclusion and Managerial implication

In general, our findings show that, any form of assistance provided by donor countries, whether material, loans or in-kind (money, infrastructure, education, humanitarian/relief items, technological transfers, health care supplies/equipment) makes a significant impact on economic development and deepens bilateral relations among countries. Hence, there should be a constant review of the existing legal framework on foreign aid policy to support and strengthen bilateral trade agreements and economic development. Because the construct variables inextricably have a link with economic development. This will help rebuild communities and lift people out of poverty, reducing the level of unemployment battling developing countries in their quest to develop and manage their economies. The application of these

research findings could serve as the foundation for future research to fill the knowledge gaps in assessing and improving the performance of the economic sector.

Although, foreign aid received from countries especially humanitarian relief may be insufficient, however, it may relieve developing countries a bit from poverty and hunger. This research is in support of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal one (1). Hence, we accept hypotheses (1, 2, 3, and 4) because of their positive impact on economic development and the strengthening of bilateral trade relations. Despite the perceived challenges associated with foreign aid/assistance in Africa which includes but are not limited to corrupt, highly inefficient management, ineffective governments, hinders economic and investment growth, stalls democracy, and the respect for rule of law as well as unstable economic policies are the only conditions that militates against Foreign Aids and economic development. This issue needs to be tackled so that foreign aid received from donors and partners cannot be mismanaged for its intended purpose. Because its management and appropriation have a significant impact on economic development, and hence cannot be overlooked in our quest to pursue economic agenda.

More importantly, ensuring successful management and inflows of foreign aid is a means to boost and sustain economic development while also deepening bilateral trade relations and donor trust. It will also aid in identifying and strengthening some important variables in the context of aid received and its repercussions on economic development. Identifying some variables of construction that have a minor impact on economic development and bilateral trade will reposition and inform managers of Aid received, as well as how to strategize and distribute the resources received to affect the economy positively, reduce poverty, hunger, and unemployment and increase infrastructural development. In a general sense, the dependence theory sought to identify and explain mutual dependence between two beings. The link between China and Nigeria and its effects on the growth of the Nigerian economy are best explained by this idea. Dependency theory holds that resources move from a "core" of wealthy governments to a "periphery" of poor and underdeveloped states, enriching the latter at the expense of the former. To a large extent, cooperating countries or groups rely on one another to achieve the desired results in this case (economic development and bilateral trade relation).

6.1 Limitations and future research

A few other research questions have remained unanswered due to the constraints imposed by the pandemic (COVID-19). The researcher, on the other hand, did everything possible to collect the desired sample for the study. The study established strong policy support for proper aid management as a prerequisite and requirement for countries to improve and build bilateral trade relations, thereby leveraging support for economic and means of bringing innovations into the country. More importantly, an additional study in other recipient countries can be conducted to investigate other variables aside from policy, poverty alleviation, infrastructural/industrial development and reducing unemployment and determine their significance on economic development.

6.2 Innovation of the paper

The study sought to mobilize policy support for proper utilization of foreign aid management and resource distribution to positively impact economic development in all aspects and deepen bilateral trade. Our findings discovered that Foreign Aid impacts positively economic development and bilateral trade relation. Notwithstanding, whether foreign aids are sufficient or insufficient, foreign aid has the potential in accelerating economic development, alleviating poverty, reducing unemployment, and increasing industrialization and infrastructural development. Foreign Aid and economic development, on the other hand, are inextricably linked. Hence, foreign aid correlates significantly with economic development. The application of these research findings could serve as a means to further strengthen policy on foreign aid assistance given to countries including Nigeria. At the moment, no such specific work has been done in Nigeria in

terms of regressing and establishing the impact of Chinese Foreign Aid, poverty alleviation, reduced unemployment, increased industrialization/infrastructure on economic development, and deepening bilateral trade relations between countries. This is a study that found a statistically significant relationship between the construct variables of interest. As a result, this is an area that requires much attention for a policy initiative focused on its impact on economic success.

Authors' Contributions

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